

DIDACTIC OPPORTUNITIES OF DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL PLATFORMS AND INTERACTIVE METHODS IN THE TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract. In the contemporary, didactic opportunities of digital educational platforms and interactive methods in the teaching foreign languages plays a crucial role in society. In particular, the youth use from digital technologies due to effectively learning of the foreign languages. The article studies to importance, educational system and processes of digital educational platforms and interactive methods in the teaching foreign languages. For example, learning foreign language works with different mobile devices, online courses, programs, interactive methods and platforms. They give a number of opportunities for creating of the new skills. Digital educational platforms are not only help to learning of the foreign language, but it also high contribute to work of interactive methods. The article reviews about controversial matters and its effectiveness.

Key words: digital educational platforms, technology, didactic opportunities, interactive methods learning foreign language, educational system, different app.

INTRODUCTION

In the recent years, education is developing intensively with digital educational technologies as it provides foreign language learners of easy and quick learning during teaching process of foreign languages. Essentially, it contribute to creating of their convenience and advantage sides. Include in: save study time, creativity and critical thinking, working of individual pace with appropriate time and place and increasing of motivation. Most young people are constrating on saving study time since it brings on doing different functions of digital educational platforms and apps such as a meaning of preparing, maintaining and storing informations. Also, it contributes to optimizing and modeling educational process.

It supports to students' creative potential and the improvement of critical thinking due to the fact that development of the students mental activities and thinking situations.

Digital educational platforms give a number of opportunities which learning foreign language at an individual pace choosing a convenient time and place of work.

Students engaged in implementation of foreign language activity and cognitive interest through the increasing motivations is that teacher should encourage and reward with high scores or present to young learners

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Methodology has important role for teaching and learning process that local and foreign researchers more analyze and research to importance of digital technologies and interactive methods in teaching foreign languages. Local researchers G'aniyeva and Z. Turaeva study and give thought to priority of technologies in the education system. Her work make reference actively participation, interesting of lesson, strengthing of knowledge as well as contribution of understanding through digital technologies or modern educational apps.

Admittedly, using of game technologies and multimedias offer a number of options which their easy and effective learning foreign languages in these years.

Foreign researchers J.Harmer of "The practice of English language teaching" book underemployed utilization of innovative methods.

"Implicit and explicit learning of language" book written by N.Ellis. The book refers about language of natural individualization and interactive educational relations.

Teacher use variety of methods during teaching foreign language. Modern teacher frequent use to check their knowledge or understanding of topics with "Kahoot" "Quiz" or "Wordwall". Foreign language learner work with "ScoreUp", "Duoling", "IELTS speaking practice", "Elsa speak" and "Quizlet" platforms. Technologies provide in their concentration and engaging during interactive lesson.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Researches of digital educational platforms and interactive methods in the teaching foreign languages show high quality results. Students of United States of America increase to 25 percent their vocabulary grammatical knowledge with digital educational platforms. According to IELTS exam's results, the middle result included in 5.5 level in 2023 year, but middle result changed 6.0 level in 2024, in Uzbekistan. The digital technologies positive effect on development of education systems.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this article is make reference to digital educational programs and interactive methods in the teaching foreign languages and young people also more support to this idea as they provide opportunities such as convenient and quality knowledge. In essential, they save their time and might learn to foreign language anytime and anyplace without problems by digital educational platforms. To succeed in digital technologies and interactive methods, they are necessary and beneficial as a consequence of development of learning and teaching foreign languages.

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